

THE DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE OF HIGH PERFORMANCE UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE TUBULAR JOINTS

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SUMMARY: This paper considers some of the issues raised in the design and manufacture of truss structures based on the use of unidirectional CFRP tubes. One critical factor in the minimisation of weight is the maximisation of operating strains in the tubular members. To achieve high strain levels without an excessive increment in manufacturing cost requires careful design of the jointing system. Two approaches are reported here, the first relies on a bonded joint, using a constant thickness tube with minimal preparation. The second uses a tapered seat mechanical joint, which adds some cost and complexity to the tube and weight and complexity to the end joint. Results are presented for both types of joint and possibilities for improvement are discussed.

KEYWORDS: tubular joints, bonded joints, mechanical joints, unidirectional materials

INTRODUCTION

In principle, the use of unidirectional carbon fibre composites permits the design and manufacture of components and structures of outstanding performance and minimum weight. One way of achieving this performance in practical applications is via the use of a truss structure and such structures have been widely used in the design and manufacture of satellite and other space structures, (Refs 1,2,3). Many such structures are deflection limited and as such operate at relatively low strains, being primarily driven by stiffness and thermal stability. For these structures the performance of end connections may not be a critical issue. For structures that are not deflection limited, the performance will depend to a large extent on the allowable strains in the truss members, which depends in turn on the strength of the end connections. High levels of operating strain remote from the end connections can simply be achieved by tapering off the thickness of the tube at some distance from the joint. This practice adds weight to both the tubes and the end fittings, (as the end fittings must become larger to accommodate the greater outside diameter of the tube). In addition the costs of the tubular elements will be increased, and the complexity of the assembly is increased as each tube must be manufactured to the specific length required, rather than being cut to length from a standard tube. If the increases in tube allowable strain due to tapering the tube remote from the end joints are sufficient this option may be the most weight effective, but this will not always be the case. The work reported here was aimed at developing end joint geometries that permitted the maximum working strains to be achieved. The baseline chosen was the use of a bonded joint of double lap shear geometry. This option was explored analytically and

practically and the results compared to an approach based on moulding in a tapered root geometry into which loads can be transferred via a mechanical joint type.

THE DOUBLE LAP SHEAR JOINT

The design of double lap shear tubular joints was based on an understanding of flat laminate joints developed in another part of the overall programme. The critical features of this understanding are noted below.

For a joint involving composite adherends a critical factor in maximising joint strength is the avoidance of interlaminar failure in the composite induced by peel forces. To ensure that this failure mode is suppressed a long adhesive chamfer beyond the end of the outer adherend is introduced into the design and the outer adherend is also chamfered back to minimise stiffness mismatch stresses at the end of the joint, fig 1, ref 4. The initiation of failure in the adhesive then appears to be in the region of the tip of the chamfer in the outer adherend (point X in fig 1). The tensile strain in the adhesive rises from the end of the fillet, at which point it must match the strain in the centre adherend, until it reaches the tip of the chamfer on the outer adherend. This rise is associated with load transfer across the joint and is non-linear in form. In principle, the tensile strain reaches infinity at the geometrical singularity at the tip of the outer adherend chamfer. In the FE modelling, the value of the predicted tensile strain at this point is mesh dependent and rises rapidly as the mesh size is reduced, as would be expected for a geometrical singularity. The geometry that is being modelled is idealised with sharp edges. In the real case there will be some level of rounding that serves to avoid the infinity suggested by the geometrical singularity.

Despite this, there will be an extremely large strain concentration at the tip of the adherend which would be expected to lead to adhesive failure at an end load much less than that experienced. Equally, if the precise level of geometrical rounding was the only relevant factor, a high level of sample to sample variability in end load carrying capacity would be expected. This is not seen in practice, with specimens that are quite different in terms of very detailed geometry at the tip of the outer adherend having very similar strengths. There are, perhaps, three factors that serve to ameliorate the effects of this extreme stress concentration.

Fig 1. Geometry of the flat double lap shear joint

The first is that the peak strains are localised into a very small volume such that the fracture toughness of the adhesive is sufficient to prevent propagation of damage on energetic grounds. The second is that the volume of the region immediately surrounding this zero failure probability zone is still very small. It is in this region, where stresses and strains are still very high, that nucleation and propagation of failure is expected. In such small volumes

of highly stressed material, it is to be expected that statistical effects will be of great importance in determining the probability of failure, via a strength/volume relationship. The third factor is that the high peak strains experienced can be equated to high local strain rates, even when the specimen as a whole is experiencing moderate strain rates. The adhesives used are strain rate sensitive materials, being both stronger and exhibiting higher moduli at high strain rates. It seems most likely that the first two effects are more important than the third, but all three may influence the strengths experienced in practice. The use of these geometrical features has been seen to lead to flat double lap shear joints of very high performance with operating strains over 0.8% at failure, with failure occurring outside the joint region, this work is reported in ref 5.

The work on tubular joints built upon the understanding of the features that lead to good performance in laminar joints (ref 6) by a consideration of how the change in geometry changes the stress state in the joints. The principal difference between flat and tubular joints is that there is a higher degree of constraint in the tubular case, especially when metallic and composite adherends are used together. This shows up most when the influence of thermally induced stresses is considered. The adhesive performance required for the targets of this programme is only available from systems that are cured at high temperature. On cooling down from cure to room temperature, substantial strains can be induced. In the flat laminate case the strain in the through thickness direction can be completely relieved, in the tubular case this is locked in, resulting in higher strains in the adhesive. Predicted joint strengths are therefore lower than for flat double lap shear joints, and are lower for titanium end pieces than for CFRP end pieces, reflecting the differences in coefficient of thermal expansion. The selection procedure for the adhesives to be used in the bonded tubular joints was based on the factors noted below.

- High lap shear strength
- High strain to failure
- Lap shear strength > 20MPa between -50 & 100⁰C
- Good hot/wet properties
- Adhesive must be readily filletable
- Low coefficient of thermal expansion
- Cure T compatible with rest of structure: < 180⁰C
- Low Poisson's ratio
- Good bonding to CFRP & titanium
- Low viscoelasticity
- Minimal moisture pickup
- Minimal effect from immersion in water or other fluids such as fuel.

On the basis of manufacturer's data and in-house testing adhesive grade 3448 from 3M was selected for trials. The 3448 material is a paste development of an aerospace grade film adhesive.

The unidirectional tubes were of two designs. The first was a conventional tubular prepreg lay-up of Toray T800 fibres in an Hexcel 924 matrix (specimen A). The second utilised a novel reinforcement form consisting of precured rods of IM7 fibre in an epoxy matrix. This reinforcement is manufactured by Neptco Inc under the name of Graphlite[®] (specimen B).

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The reinforcement is claimed to lead to superior product performance by ensuring that fibres are straight and that this straightness is maintained throughout lay-up and cure. For conversion into tubular form 0.74mm rods were used and set into film adhesive with surface plies of T800/924 prepreg to ensure a good bonding surface. The end fitting was manufactured from titanium alloy, to the design shown in fig 2.

The design and manufacture of efficient double lap shear tubular joints is much more complex than for flat laminate double lap shear joints. Issues such as how to prepare the inside surface of a tube for bonding and how to ensure that the necessary fillets and chamfers are achieved on the inside of a tube have to be tackled prior to any manufacture and test of joints. The use of a pressure fed grit blasting machine was used to prepare both inside and outside surfaces of the tube and end fitting.

Fig 2. Schematic design of tubular double lap shear joint

The necessity to have a double lap shear joint is met by the use of a centre pin with a flared end for load transfer into the joint body.

Small machined PTFE spacers are used to generate the required fillet geometries and an alignment jig is used to form the outer fillet and hold all parts in register. A small rebate has been machined into both centre pin and body to increase the available size of adhesive fillet at the back of the joint. Despite this the absolute size of the rear fillet is considerably less than that of the front fillet. However, the increase in diameter of the body prior to the start of the rear fillet should tend to de-stress this region such that the small fillet volume does not lead to premature failure. Joint overlap length is set at 50mm. Minor misalignments with respect to the test machine will be taken out via the pinned spigots. A taper is created on the CFRP tube using high speed rotary burrs. Tube ID is 10mm and OD is 13mm. Bond line thickness is 0.7mm.

Tube Joint Test Results

Double lap shear tube joints have been tested. The first was made up from 0.74mm carbon fibre rods as described earlier. A small hole was drilled in the titanium joint body to permit adhesive to be injected into the joint. This proved to be very difficult due to the extreme viscosity and viscoelasticity of the 3M3448 adhesive used. These properties of the uncured

adhesive give it excellent gap filling and non-slump characteristics, and are thus ideal for flat double lap shear joints, but make it more difficult to utilise in the tubular joint case.

The assembled tube and end joints was tested in an Instron servohydraulic tensile testing machine under position control.

Specimen A was tested with failure occurring at 32kN

Failure occurred by a partial failure of the bond line at each end, allowing the tube to split into two parts longitudinally, as shown in fig 3. An examination of the failed joints showed that the adhesive had not penetrated between the tube and the centre pin so that the tube was, in effect, bonded as a single lap joint rather than a double lap joint.

Fig 3. General features of failed tube test specimen

Specimen B utilised a T800/924 prepreg tube and 3M3448 adhesive. In this case, excess adhesive was introduced into the end fittings and the tube was driven into place whilst being revolved, driving out excess adhesive. This meant that the PTFE centre piece shown in fig 2 could not be employed. Failure in this joint occurred at 56kN; failure occurred primarily at the bond line between the outer Ti element of the fitting and the adhesive. The adhesive thickness in the joint was rather variable with some voidage visible, although not in regions of peak stresses. The adhesive thickness variation is caused by a slight misalignment between the tube and end fitting of about 0.6° (0.5mm in 50mm). As designed the inner Ti pin should end at the same position as the outer Ti tube. In this test specimen the inner pin has not been seated fully home and the end of the inner pin is about 7mm short of the end of the outer tube. See fig 4.

Fig 4. Cross section through failed joint. (Outer adherend not shown).

The inner bond line appears to be completely intact and the titanium pin has failed at its minimum cross section, see fig 2. This is assumed to be as a result of the outer bond line failure, rather than vice versa. Taking an average circumference of 11.5mm for the tube (10mm ID, 13mm OD) the load carrying capacity at failure was 1.55kN/mm. This equates to 1036MPa stress in the tube, or 0.67% strain. It should be noted that, as a result of the offset between inner and outer Ti adherends, the stresses in the outer fillet will be higher than expected, which will result in a reduction in the strength of the joint. We would expect to see a lower strength in tubular joints than in flat joints, as noted earlier. Using non-linear finite element analysis we can predict a strength of 57.4kN for the tubular double lap shear joint with 3M3448 adhesive. Thus the achieved joint strength is within 3% of the expected strength despite the deviations from ideal geometry. The exact mode of failure is hard to detect, as it is difficult to separate effects that initiated failure from those that occurred as a result of failure. For approximately 15mm around the circumference, there is a visible crack at the tip of the outer adherend. It may be that cracking in this region was the initiating factor and that the growing crack diverted into the titanium/adhesive interface, leading to total separation.

MECHANICAL JOINTS

The mechanical joint design was based on the same tube dimensions as the bonded joint, but instead of having a constant diameter tube a flare is introduced into the ends of the tube. The basic geometry analysed is as shown in fig 5.

Fig 5. Geometry of the mechanical joint.

The variables taken in the design and optimisation of this joint were the length and depth of the flared region, assuming a smooth flaring out from the parallel sided tube without any step or discontinuity at the interface between flared and parallel sections.

The conclusions of this analytical work were that the smallest flare generally gave the lowest stresses and that the effective stress concentration in the axial direction reduces as the joint length increases, see fig 6. The stresses were predicted using non-linear axisymmetric finite element methods. The very clear message from the analytical work is that, in contrast to bonded joints, the stress concentration at the end of the joint can be very greatly reduced, see also ref 7. This feature makes such a joint scaleable. That is to say that doubling the dimensions should give rise to a doubling of end load carrying capacity per unit joint width. This is not true for adhesive bonding and represents a severe limitation on the use of such joints at very high load intensities. On the negative side the weight of a mechanical joint will be greater than that of a bonded joint, at least for relatively low absolute levels of end load. As absolute end load increases the weight, expressed as grams per kN of end load will reduce for the mechanical joint, and this may become the lighter solution at very heavy end loads.

Fig 6. Peak axial stress for an applied load equivalent to an average axial stress of 1GPa, with respect to the geometry of the joint.

Whilst the mechanical end joint design described above should give the best performance the manufacture of such a flared tube would be expected to be very difficult. With this in mind a simplified version of the joint has been designed for initial manufacture and test trials. Instead of a constant thickness flared region, this joint has been designed as a moulded in taper based on thickening up a tube with a parallel sided bore, see fig 7.

The test piece was manufactured from T800/924 prepreg with all plies being unidirectional and aligned to the tube axis. The taper was created in the simplest way possible, by laying up additional layers of prepreg over the basic parallel lay-up prior to consolidation and autoclave cure. This approach was taken rather than that of interleaving the additional plies within the tube lay-up to minimise production costs and avoid as far as possible the formation of consolidation induced defects in the lay-up.

Fig 7. Schematic of tapered tube mechanical joint

When tested this tube gave a load at failure of 77kN. The failure mode picture was complex with failures in the composite tube at both ends, plus a smaller area of failed fibres at the middle of the tube. The failure process is believed to be as follows. Primary failure occurred at the stress concentration at the end of the taper as shown in fig 7. This failure is clearly tensile. Secondary failure is then believed to have occurred at the other end of the tube at the

end of the metallic joint piece. This failure is clearly compressive and probably arose as a consequence of sudden relaxation of the test machine. The last failure is believed to be at the centre of the tube where, either sudden bending applied as a result of test machine relaxation or stress wave reflection caused a very localised failure. No evidence can be seen of any delamination from the ends of the additional plies used to build up the external taper up to a magnification of $\times 100$. The failure load equates to 2120N/mm or 1413MPa (0.92% strain, requiring a stress concentration of ~ 1.7 to induce failure). This is the highest stress we have achieved to date in any joint style. It should be possible to improve on the design of this joint by modification of the geometry to reduce the stress concentration at the end of the taper. Fig 8. shows the load transfer region of this joint at actual size to give an impression of how little composite material is needed to transfer a load of 7.8 tonnes.

*Fig 8. Load transfer region of joint. Scale 1:1.
Weight of load transfer zone less than 5gr*

This simpler, but easily achievable, design shows a much more sudden change of geometry at the end of the load transfer region than the baseline flared geometry and, as expected, this results in a higher effective stress concentration in this case; $\times 1.7$ compared to $\times 1.2$ for the smoothly flared design.

DISCUSSION

A very good understanding of the factors leading to high strength in tubular double lap shear joints has been developed. The critical features are achieving a tapered adhesive fillet beyond the end of the adherends to minimise peel stresses within the laminate and tapering of the adherend tips to minimise the stresses within the adhesive layer. Together these features lead to a failure mode that makes the maximum use of the available adhesive tensile strength and strain capability. More effort is required to develop the capability of accurately predicting tubular double lap shear strength. Titanium end fittings have been developed for tubular double lap shear joints. Further effort is required in the development of assembly methods for tubular double lap shear joints. It is much more difficult to achieve the necessary features in the adhesive layer in the tubular format, compared to the flat format, as access is not available to the inside of the joint. The rheological and application properties of the adhesive that lead to good performance in flat format lead to difficulties in the manufacture of tubular double lap shear joints. Future efforts will be concentrated on how we can achieve the correct geometry with the currently selected adhesive as this is capable of giving exceptional strength. However, in parallel we will continue to seek adhesives with improved application properties for the tubular joints. Despite the difficulties with manufacture of the more complex tubular joints and the expectation of lower strengths due to an increased constraint and increased thermal stresses we have achieved a high working strain at failure in the tubular bonded joints. The maximum strain at failure achieved to date is 0.67% for a joint of imperfect geometry. This compares favourably with the maximum working strain achieved in flat double lap shear joints, being about 80% of that value, despite additional constraints and imperfect geometry. The unresolved difficulties with respect to achievement of a perfect

geometry will have to be overcome before we can identify the maximum working strains and hence load carrying capacity in a tubular joint.

A very good understanding of the factors leading to high strength in tubular mechanical joints has been developed. The elements of a practical tubular mechanical joint have been designed and acquired. Preliminary results from tubular mechanical joints show the highest end load carrying capacity of any joint style tested to date. Failure in the tube at a stress of 1413MPa was achieved, demonstrating that very high loads can be transferred into tubular UD members. This stress equates to 0.92% strain, a value 10% above the best flat double lap shear joint value achieved to date and 37% above the best tubular double lap shear joint value achieved to date. Further optimisation of these mechanical joints should be possible, permitting even higher end loads to be carried.

A realistic comparison between the bonded and mechanically jointed tubular members depends on more than a simple consideration of relative working strains, we need to look at the potential applications to put the two designs into focus. The single greatest advantage of the bonded solution is probably that joints can be made at any point. This means that we can procure tubing in long lengths, cut these to size and bond them together without having to make a different tube for each length. Thus the tooling bill for any particular assembly is kept to a minimum. Equally, the length tolerance on each tube can be relatively relaxed, especially if the joint is designed so as to destress the rear of the joint. Thus potential problems of tolerance build up during the assembly of a truss can be avoided. One disadvantage is that, as we have seen, assembly can present problems and only an external inspection of the joint is possible, although some internal defects may be detectable by NDT. Perhaps the greatest disadvantage is that absolute levels of end load are limited. Whilst it is true that high levels of working strain can be achieved, this is only possible in relatively thin walled tubing so that for a high end loading a large number of tubes and end fittings are required. Even this "disadvantage" may sometimes have positive implications as a large number of tubes has benefits with respect to structural redundancy. The actual end fittings are fairly straightforward to manufacture by normal metalworking techniques, either by turning or potentially by casting.

For the mechanically jointed option the actual end fittings are harder to manufacture. When a tube is flared out at both ends the element of the end fitting that directly interacts with the tube must be split to permit assembly and a separate external collar must be used to react the loads imposed by the tension in the tube. This means that the joints can be assembled and disassembled, which in turn gives the potential for proof testing of each and every tube and joint prior to assembly into a structure. Because these joints lack the stress and strain singularities that bedevil the analysis of bonded joints, and make strength predictions so difficult, they should be scalable to thicker tubes without leading to the reduction in composite adherend working strains that is associated with bonded joints. This means that the number of both tubes and joints can be below that required for bonded tube structures, if the structures must be designed to carry high loads. Of course, if less elements are used to carry a given load the level of redundancy is also declining. The considerable benefits of the mechanical end joints are not without costs; these include a requirement to make a different moulding for each tube length required, with tooling and manufacturing scheduling implications. In addition the tolerancing requirements on tube length can become very tight when the tubes are required to interact with rigid and fixed end pieces.

For any particular structure one may be able to define which approach is optimal in terms of weight, cost, complexity, redundancy, inspectability etc. In the general case, no specific conclusion can be reached as to which design is to be preferred, what can be said is that both designs are capable of further development beyond the state presented here and that improvements should be possible on the 0.67% and 0.92% strains at failure reported here. Both these strain values are well beyond those currently used for design purposes in most applications of CFRP. The future developments of improved jointing techniques can make a major impact on the weight, manufacturability and costs of composite structures, the work presented here is only a first step in the right direction.

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